

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE SILK ROAD HISTORIOGRAPHY

Khushvaktov Nodirjon

Silk Road International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11216584>

Abstract. *The Great Silk Road contributed not only to trade between regions but also to the exchange of civilizations between peoples and continents, and served as an important tool for the development of cultural values, science and cities, thereby creating conditions for intercultural dialogue. The article provides a comparative analysis of the study of the history of the ancient Great Silk Road, crossing Eurasia, in domestic and foreign historiography. The coverage of all aspects of the emergence and development of the Great Silk Road in domestic and foreign literature is determined using the methodology of comparative analysis. The final part of the article contains an analysis and update of the historical data studied on the topic. The article presents information about the modern methodology of studying the Great Silk Road by applying research methods used in European countries in the field of historiography. The important aspects of the Great Silk Road in the interdependence of the Eurasian countries in the cultural and humanitarian spheres are highlighted based on information from the foreign scientific literature. Useful models for researching the historiographical aspects of research using visual materials are explained. Through the comparative method, which is one of the methods of historical research, the degree of research on the Great Silk Road in European, American and Asian historiography was analyzed. Using modern analytical methods, the level of study of the scientific and educational-methodological aspects of the history of the Silk Road was analyzed by scientists of the socio-humanitarian field in different interpretations. As a result of the research, recommendations on the modern methodology of researching the Great Silk Road were presented.*

Keywords: *the Great Silk Road, historiography, source studies, China, Samarkand, Europe, Asia, civilization, culture, historical literature, comparative analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

The Great Silk Road is one of the indispensable phenomenal phenomena of human history, and from its creation to the 16th century (when the importance of land trade routes decreased due to the discovery of waterways during the period of the Great Geographical Discoveries), it permeated all aspects of the past of the peoples of Eurasia.

The main goal of our research is the comparative analysis of the creation of the Great Silk Road and the role of cities in its domestic, foreign trade, economic and cultural relations through foreign historiography written based on modern research methods.

The scientific analysis of the literature on the history of the Great Silk Road by European and Asian historians is based on a comparative research methodology. The Great Silk Road contributed not only to trade between regions but also to the exchange of civilizations between peoples and continents, and served as an important tool for the development of cultural values, science and cities, thereby creating conditions for intercultural dialogue. The article provides a comparative analysis of the study of the history of the ancient Great Silk Road, crossing Eurasia, in domestic and foreign historiography. The coverage of all aspects of the emergence and development of the Great Silk Road in domestic and foreign literature is determined using the

methodology of comparative analysis. The final part of the article contains an analysis and update of the historical data studied on the topic.

The Great Silk Road was the basis for trade between nations and the exchange of civilizations between nations and cities. Intercultural values between cities have played an important role in the development of science, and thus in the context of inter-civilizational dialogue. This research paper provides information on the study of the history of the ancient Silk Road through Eurasia in European and Asian historiography. The methodology of comparative research was chosen as the method of research work. Also, the main part of the work is a comparative analysis of the research work of Chinese historians and European Chinese historians. The Great Silk Road is a historical phenomenon currently the subject of extensive research in various fields worldwide. It is also possible to make an in-depth scientific comparative analysis of the fundamental significance of the national cultural heritage of the East and the West, which has been exchanged along the historical path, through this broad and meaningful historical significance.

The methodology of historical science has a basic concept called historical knowledge or historical knowledge. If we focus on the descriptions of the concepts of historical knowledge in the way of the subject of history, we can see that they are mutually integrated. The creation of the Great Silk Road can be considered one of the most phenomenal historical processes in the history of mankind. The Great Silk Road, which acted as a bridge to the convergence of socio-economic, political, and spiritual changes taking place in Eastern and Western societies, served as a basis for the development of innovation in Eurasian society as a whole. For example, when scientific research works on the historiography of Central Asia are analyzed, similarities disappear in their way. Because, historically, the peoples of Central Asia have lived together as a whole.

THE SILK ROAD: A BRIDGE BETWEEN HISTORY AND THE PRESENT

The terminology Great Silk Road was not used in ancient times. The scientific study of the historical, geographical, and cultural aspects of the Great Silk Road began in practice in the second half of the 19th century by scholars in many countries. Scientists from Western Europe, Russia, China and Japan have made significant contributions to the historical research study of the history of the Silk Road. In particular, the Great Silk Road Encyclopedia was published in Japan. In 1877, the famous German scientist Ferdinand von Richthofen, in his major scientific work *China*, called the system of roads connecting different parts of the vast Eurasian continent the Silk Road, and later adopted the term "Great Silk Road".

Foreign historians include Peter Frankopan, Agnew Neville, Valeria Hansen, Nils Ambolt, Prabodh Chandra, Beckwith Christopher, Blunt Wilfrid, Bonavia Judy, Hedin Sven, Hopkirk Peter, Liu Xinru, Nebenzahl Kenneth, Tucker Jonathan, Wh. Monica, Wood Frances, Nile Green, Jacqueline Moore, Bernard Ollivier, Punsara Amarasinghe and many other foreign historians.

The history of Samarkand, located at the crossroads of civilizations connecting the eastern and western branches of the Great Silk Road, is being thoroughly studied by historians of the modern world in a way that connects it to the history of world civilization. Samarkand has served as the capital of the great city of great states and empires of all ages. This article examines the place of Samarkand in the history of the Great Silk Road and a comparative analysis of scientific research written by a group of foreign historians and tourists. At the end of the research, clear scientific conclusions were made about the importance of the literature used in the historiography of the Great Silk Road. The main task of the research is to study the scientific facts written by foreign historians based on sources on the history of Central Asia.

The Great Silk Road left an indelible mark on the history of mankind as a path of inter-civilizational dialogue, historically linking the West and East in the field of culture, economy, and social life. Uzbekistan is a unique historical region where West and East meet, and the merit of the Great Silk Road in bringing the two sides of the world closer together and in the integrity of human civilization is invaluable. The fact Silk Road, as a trade, economic and socio-cultural road network, which is important for the history of mankind, does not lose its significance to this day, the role of many ancient peoples of the world with a rich material and cultural heritage plays an important role.

The Great Silk Road is one of such ancient main routes that connected the West and the East for several millennia. This path was introduced into science under the name "Silk Road" by the German scientist Ferdinand von Richthofen in the 70s of the XIX century. This is stated in the work of Richthofen "China". Before him, this road was called "Western meridional road". It should be noted that before the Great Silk Road, there were also such roads as the Lalsky way, and the Shah way, connecting the peoples of Central Asia and the East.

Historical sources write that the period of the first rise in trade relations on the Great Silk Road - the 3rd century BC - refers to the 3rd century AD. During this period, on the eastern side of the Silk Road was the empire of the Huns, and on the western side – was the Achaemenid Empire of Iran in 558-330. BC e. In the 3rd century, the state of Kang existed on the territory of modern Southern Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. During this period, the Achaemenids took control of part of the trade route. In the III-IV centuries. BC e. China and Central Asia split into small states that did not remain without influence on road development. The Great Silk Road dates back to another period of its heyday in the 6th-12th centuries AD. This period coincides with the period of strengthening the Turkic Khaganate. The Silk Road was merged in China with the Tang Empire (618-907).

The creation of relevant historical methodological foundations for studying the history of cities located on the Great Silk Road is aimed at an in-depth analysis of the level of their study by the scientific community and the application of methods recognized abroad, for which, first of all, it is necessary to determine in which direction the scientific research problem is directed. When conducting scientific research in the field of historiography, one of the priority tasks is, first of all, the selection of selected scientific literature following its various levels.

The Great Silk Road throughout its vast history of mankind for several millennia was characterized by its special historical character as a path of trade and intercultural communication between various peoples of the East and West.

In Uzbekistan and foreign historiography, the study of the history of the Great Silk Road is one of the areas of particular importance and is still being studied by historians as an actual area of historical scientific research. Central network routes run from the ancient cities of Uzbekistan, the most important of which is the Silk Road. Therefore, historians who conducted historical scientific research on the history of these cities will certainly touch on the history of the Silk Road. The relevance of the topic lies in the fact that by studying the past of this historically significant path, we can explore aspects of the relationship between Asian and European states with the valuable information that we know to this day.

On the topic "Comparative analysis of the history of the cities of the Great Silk Road in foreign historiography", effectively using the scientific methodology of comparative analysis of research works of historians of Asia and Europe, we will present our considerations. Until now, a group of scientists in Uzbekistan has been conducting research work on the historiography of the

Great Silk Road. As a result of scientific research, we divided the historiography the study of the Great Silk Road by region as follows: the study of the historiography of the Great Silk Road in the states of Western Europe; The study of the historiography of the Great Silk Road in Asian states. Study of the history of the Silk Road mainly by historians of China, India, South Korea and Japan; in Central Asia, special attention is paid to studying the history of the Great Silk Road. Because this area is considered one of the most important on the trade route. In particular, in the work of Mahmud Kashgari "Devoni lugotit-Turk," a Japanese is mentioned, who calls him "Yabarka" and is considered a great scientist who first put this country on his map. According to the results of archaeological research, today the spread of the teachings of Buddhism is proven, that existed in the social and spiritual life of ancient Uzbekistan in the 6th century AD, from the territory of the Kushan state along the Great Silk Road to China, Korea and Japan.

SILK ROAD LITERATURES REVIEWS

Let us dwell on some historical studies of individual branches of the Great Silk Road, their place and their role in historical eras. In these research topics, A.R. Muhammadjonov, T. Nigmatov, V. A. Shishkin, and A. Yu It is believed that Yakubovskiy, in his scientific research, thought deeply about the role of the Great Silk Road in human civilization. Of the domestic scientists involved in the study of the history of the Great Silk Road, academician Edward Rtveladze, Ablat Khodzhaev, O.P. Kobzeva¹, Abdukhalik Abdurasul ugli, A.K. Kirgizboev, A. Berdimurodov², A. Anarbaev, G. A. Agzamov, A. Aitboev, O. Mavlonov³ and several other historians covered some aspects of the topic in their research work. In the scientific studies of these authors, such issues as the emergence of the Great Silk Road and its main branches, the Trade of individual states, cities built on the Silk Road, and the mutual intercultural interaction of peoples on the Silk Road are considered.

The book of the famous archaeologist, academician Rtveladze Edward Vasilievich "The Great Silk Road" tells about the historical places of the Great Silk Road, which passed through the territory of Uzbekistan. The book contains information about the Chinese settlements of the Great Silk Road associated with the activities of ancient Uzbek traders. Ablat Khodzhaev's book "The Great Silk Road: Relations and Destinies" contains a lot of scientific information about the history of the Silk Road.⁴ It can be said that Abdurasul oglu Abdurasul is the author of "The Great Silk Road"⁵, "Chin and Machin" and other studies of scientific literature. Cooperation of Uzbekistan with the countries of Asia on the restoration of the Great Silk Road A.K. Kirgizboev's analysis is given in the monograph "International cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the countries of Asia".

In the writings of Chinese historians, it is stated that in the 4th century BC, Chinese fabrics appeared in India and European countries. In India, these fabrics were called "Cina patta", in European countries - "magic". And the country that grew silk was called "Serika". While most Chinese scientists believe that Serika was named after China, another group of scientists - Khori

¹ Kobzeva O.P., Djalilov O.Z. (2015) Uzbekistan and China on the Silk route (Monograph). – Tashkent.103 p.

² **Berdimurodov A. (2017) The Great Silk Road. Uzbekistan Publishing House. Tashkent press. 197 p.**

³ Mavlonov O. (2001) From the history of the formation and development of ancient roads in Central Asia. Collection of materials of the Republican conference.-Tashkent: Academy. 112

⁴ Khojayev A. (2007) The Great Silk Road: relations and destinies.-Tashkent: UzME,280 p.

⁵ Abdukholik A. (1994) The Great Silk Road // Communication.Tashkent. 54-65-p.

wrote that Serika is Kashgaria in the 5th century BC in Greece, long clothes were sewn from silk fabric, which was called - "Amorgiam" since the name of the fabric was considered "Amorgis".

The Chinese scholar Li Minwei argued that the areas connecting the northern provinces of China with the Mediterranean Sea consisted of Mesopotamia, the Iranian Plateau, and the territories of Central Asia to the east of this sea. About the distribution of silk in Central Asia in this place, archaeologist A. Askarov, pointing to the age of the remnants of silk found on the Sopollitepa monument in Surkhandarya, 3600-3700 years old, previously claimed that silk was created in our country even before China.

In researching the history of Uzbekistan, studying the history of the Great Silk Road is one of the new directions in teaching students the history of Uzbekistan. Many of our scientists have researched the formation of the Great Silk Road, and its contribution to world development.

The book "The Great Silk Road" contains a lot of information about the historical sites of the Great Silk Road through the territory of Uzbekistan, the famous archaeologist, academician Rtveldze Edward. The book contains information about the sites of the Great Silk Road, which is associated with the activities of Chinese merchants of ancient Uzbekistan. Ablat Khujayev's book, "Great Silk Road: Attitudes and Destinies", contains a wealth of scientific information on the history of the Silk Road. We can mention the research of Abdukhalik Abdurasul oglu "The Great Silk Road", "Chin and Machin" and others. The cooperation of Uzbekistan with Asian countries on the restoration of the Great Silk Road is analyzed in depth in the monograph of A. Kyrgyzbaev "International cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan with Asian countries."

Although studies have expressed some opinions concerning this topic, the modern methodological analysis of historiography has not been proven. For this, one should turn to foreign historiography. A large number of scientific studies have been carried out on this topic by historians of developed foreign countries. One of the main objectives of the study is an in-depth scientific analysis of research conducted in foreign countries and the widespread involvement of new historical knowledge in the study of the history of the Great Silk Road in Uzbekistan.

Foreign historians, Peter Frankopan⁶, Agnew Neville⁷, Valeria Hansen⁸, Nils Ambolt, Prabodh Chandra, Christopher Beckwith⁹ [10], and Wilfried Blunt¹⁰ participated in the study of the topic, Bonavia Judy¹¹, Hedin Sven¹², Hopkirk Peter¹³, Liu Xingru¹⁴, Nebenzya

⁶ Frankon. P. (2015) *The Silk Roads (a new history of the world)*. – London. Bloomsbury Press. 656 p

⁷ Agnew Neville. (1997) *Conservation of Ancient Sites on the Silk Road*. Los Angeles, The Getty Conservation Institute. 112 p.

⁸ Hansen. V.(2012) *Silk Road a new history*. -London. Oxford university Press. ISBN139780190218423. 320 p

⁹ Beckwith Christopher. (2009) *Empires of the Silk Road. A History of Central Eurasia from the Bronze Age to the Present*. Princeton, Princeton University Press. 7-12 p

¹⁰ Blunt, Wilfrid. (1973) *The Golden Road to Samarkand*. London, Hamish Hamilton. 17-23 p.

¹¹ Bonavia Judy. (1992) *The Silk Road. Xi'an to Kashgar*. Hong Kong, Odyssey. 3-8 p

¹² Hedin, Sven. (1938) *The Silk Road*. London, George Routledge & Sons Ltd. 5p.

¹³ Hopkirk, Peter. (1980) *Foreign Devils on the Silk Road. The Search for the Lost Cities and Treasures of Chinese Central Asia*. London, John Murray.

¹⁴ Liu, Xinru. (2010) *The Silk Road in World History*. New York, Oxford University Press. 3-12 p.

Kenneth¹⁵, Tucker Jonathan¹⁶, Whitfield Susan¹⁷, Whitlock Monica¹⁸, Wood France¹⁹, Neil Green²⁰, Jacqueline Moore²¹, Bernard Olivier²² and others, this is reflected in the scientific research of many foreign historians.

Valeria Hansen's scientific work titled "A New History of the Silk Road" provides a clear explanation of the city of Samarkand with the countries of the West and the East using the method of comparative analysis. Dedicated to the fundamental history of this Great Silk Road by Hansen. This literature consists of an introduction, 7 chapters and a final part. Chapter 4 of the work, namely "The Motherland of the Sogdians. The section "Silk Road traders in Samarkand and Sogdiana" is dedicated to Samarkand, one of the main cities of the Great Silk Road. V. Hansen's book, based on scientific facts, tells about the centre of the ancient Sogdian country of Samarkand, which is the main branch of the Great Silk Road, and about the Sogdians who have lived here for a long time. Hansen's book, based on scientific facts, contains information about the city of Samarkand, the centre of the ancient Sogdian region, which is the main branch of the Great Silk Road, and the ancient Sogdians who lived here²³.

One of the objects that serve as a basis for revealing the aspects of the history of the Great Silk Road related to the Middle Ages is the activity of the Italian traveller and merchant Marco Polo (who travelled along the Silk Road in 1271-1295). Modern researchers have cited a lot of information about him from a number of his works. Among them, Robin Brown's "Marco Polo: the incredible journey"²⁴, Lawrence Bergreen's "Marco Polo: from Venice to Xanadu"²⁵ and Jonathan Clements' "A history of the Silk Road"²⁶ describe Marco Polo and his Silk Road. information on the historical processes related to the road.

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH METHODS ON THE SILK ROAD

The Great Silk Road, having huge potential, and huge opportunities serves as an important factor in the periods of the historical development of the countries of the East. The Great Silk Road occupies a special place in the history of mankind not only in connection with trade but also as a way of intercultural exchange between various peoples of the East and West throughout its vast history of several millennia.

Valeria Hansen's fundamental scientific work, A New History of the Silk Road, provides a clear explanation of Samarkand's method of comparative analysis with the western and eastern

¹⁵ Nebenzahl Kenneth. (2004) Mapping the Silk Road and Beyond. 2000 Years of Exploring the East. New York, Phaidon Press.

¹⁶ Tucker Jonathan. (2003) The Silk Road. Art and History. London, Philip Wilson. 24-27 p.

¹⁷ Whitfield Susan. (1999) Life Along the Silk Road. London, John Murray. 7-9 p

¹⁸ Whitlock Monica. (2002) Beyond the Oxus. The Central Asians. London, John Murray.

¹⁹ Wood Frances. (2003) The Silk Road. Two Thousand Years in the Heart of Asia. London, British Library

²⁰ Nile Green. (2014) Writing Travel in Central Asian History. Indiana university press.

²¹ Jacqueline M. Moore, Rebecca Woodward Wendelken. (2010) Teaching the Silk Road: A Guide for College Teachers. SUNY press.

²² Bernard Ollivier. (2020) Walking to Samarkand: The Great Silk Road from Persia to Central Asia. 312 p.

²³ V.Hansen. The Silk Road (A new History). 18-47 p.

²⁴ Robin Brown. Marco Polo: the incredible journey. "The History" press. 2011. 184p.

²⁵ Lourence Bergreen. Marco Polo: from Venice to Xanadu. Alfred A.Knoff press. New York. 2007. 510 p.

²⁶ Jonathan Clements. "A history of the Silk Road. House publishing. London.2017. 220 p.

countries. Dedicated to the fundamental history of this Great Silk Road by W. Hansen, it consists of the following parts: Part 1: The Kingdom of Croatia (a royal name in Chinese history) at the crossroads of Central Asian roads; Part 2: The Red and Kucha Caves at the Silk Road Gate; Part 3: Turfan between China and Iran; Section 4: Homeland of the Sogdians. Merchants of the Silk Road in Samarkand and Sogdiana; Part 5: The historic Chang'an, modern Xi'an cities at the cosmopolitan terminal of the Silk Road; Chapter 6: The Time Capsule of the History of the Silk Road. Dunhuang Caves; Section 7: Hotan - Access Road to Xinjiang for Buddhism and Islam; Summary part. History of land roads throughout Central Asia. The role of the peoples of the world with a rich ancient material and cultural heritage is important for the Silk Road to remain an important trade, the economic and socio-cultural network for human history. Among such peoples were the Sogdians living in and around the ancient city of Samarkand²⁷.

The author of the book "Treasures of the Great Silk Road" was a Czech writer and historian E. Knobloch (1927-2013), a scholar of the history of Central Asia and the Islamic world. He studied Middle Eastern history at Charles University and the Oriental Institute in Prague. In 1959 he visited Central Asia. In 1999 he became a member of the Royal Geographical Society. In addition to the above-mentioned fundamental age of the author's history of Central Asia, "Central Asian Art"²⁸, "Beyond Oxus: Central Asian Archeology, Art and Architecture"²⁹, "Monuments of Central Asia: Turkestan Archeology, Handbook of Art and Architecture"³⁰, "Journey to the Heart of Asia"³¹, "Archeology and Architecture of Afghanistan"³², and "Death of Amir Temur"³³.

Edgar Knobloch's Treasures of the Great Silk Road consists of four chapters. The first section provides information on the general history of the cities along the Great Silk Road, including civilization, geography, social life and architecture. The second part is called Central Asia. The second section consists of 6 small paragraphs. They consist of subdivisions called Khorezm, Zarafshan valley, Turkmenistan, Amudarya and southern Tajikistan, Syrdarya and Fergana valleys, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan³⁴. The Treasures of the Great Silk Road provide a comprehensive account of the culture and history of Central Asia, one of the major centres of human civilization. Turkestan - the region of Central Asia and Western China - is a point of intercultural conflict between civilizations. Four major invasions - Greek, Arab, Mongol, and Russian - have left their mark on the vast region, along with Persian, Turkish, and Chinese cultural influences.

The Great Silk Road has been studied by European and Asian historians for its unique significance in human history. To determine the role of the history of the cities on the Great Silk Road in world history today, a group of foreign historians will analyze the important aspects of historiography through comparative analysis.

²⁷ V.Hansen. The Silk Road (A new History). 3 p.

²⁸ E. Knobloch. (1965) The art of Central Asia. [Paul Hamlyn](#), London.

²⁹ E. Knobloch. (1972) Beyond the Oxus: Archaeology, art & architecture of Central Asia. Benn, London. [ISBN 0-510-03351-2](#).

³⁰ E. Knobloch. (2001) Monuments of Central Asia: A guide to the archaeology, art and architecture of Turkestan. I. B. Tauris, London. [ISBN 1-86064-590-9](#).

³¹ E. Knobloch. (1962) The Heart of Asia (travel), in Czech, Prague, Bratislava.

³² E. Knobloch. (2002) The archaeology and architecture of Afghanistan. [The History Press](#), Stroud. [ISBN 0-7524-2519-6](#). 54-65 p

³³ E. Knobloch. (1965) .The Death of Tamer Lane (a novel), in Czech, Prague. 114-118 p

³⁴ E. Knobloch. (2013) Treasures of the Great Silk Road. The History press. 354 p.

Today we can find a lot of scientific, artistic and other literature on the history of the Great Silk Road published in foreign publications. The relevance of our research is that the data we are studying have not been recorded in historiography, which is still a major part of the study of the history of Uzbekistan in comparison with local data. a comparative study of new historical information about economic and cultural-enlightenment life, aimed at substantiating new directions in the existing literature.

Historian scholars have researched the history of the Great Silk Road. As a result of our scientific research, we have divided the historiography of the study of the Great Silk Road by regions into the following:

- To study the history of the Great Silk Road in Western Europe and America. A study of the history of the Silk Road, mainly by English, French, German and American historians;
- To study the history of the Great Silk Road in Asia. A study of the history of the Silk Road, mainly by historians from China, India, South Korea, and Japan;
- Special attention is paid to the study of the history of the Great Silk Road in Central Asia. Because this area is one of the most important areas of the trade route.
 - Study through Chinese manuscript sources;
 - Study through Chinese literature about Great Silk Road translated into English and Russian;
 - Study the literature of Asian, European, and American historians;
 - Study through ancient manuscript sources written in Turkish, Persian and Arabic languages;
 - Study of the Great Silk Road through research historians in Uzbekistan.

Table 1

By creating an up-to-date historical methodological framework for the study of history, the cities along the Great Silk Road have focused on an in-depth analysis of the level of study by the scientific community to date and the application of methods recognized abroad. we need to figure out exactly what direction it is headed. One of the priorities in conducting research in the field of history is, first of all, the classification of selected scientific literature according to different levels.

CONCLUSION

The Great Silk Road is not only a caravan route but also a process that has left an indelible mark on the history of Eurasian civilization and served as a great factor in its all-around development. In short, the history of the Great Silk Road can be established through large-scale

historical research, in the direction of "Scientific research of the cultural and educational heritage of the Great Silk Road." This kind of scientific research serves as a basis for us historians to study the history of the Great Silk Road in different directions and branches. In the history of Uzbekistan, there is every reason to study the Great Silk Road, because the Great Silk Road is positive for the development of science and culture of Uzbekistan, the development of ancient cities, the development of diplomacy, economic and cultural affected.

In the branches of the Great Silk Road from East to West, the unification of nomadic and urban peoples, the end of the Middle Ages and the beginning of the new era was an important period for cultural prosperity with rich artistic architectural styles and ornaments. This play, which provides information about the Central Asian region located on the Great Silk Road, is filled with quotations from the works of modern travellers, closely intertwined with the comments of an international expert on the archaeological, architectural and decorative features of the cities described by the author. You can meet The photos, which provide valuable information, include the latest changes in the boundaries of the region on many maps. This book provides important information not only for historians but also for those who are interested in the great cultural heritage of the region, as well as for travellers to the region.

Our study is aimed at a comparative analysis of the study of the history of the cities of Central Asia on the Great Silk Road by foreign historians. To start a new direction in the study of foreign historiography, using, first of all, the scientific research of scientists from the most developed foreign universities today, analyzing and implementing as samples brochures published in internationally recognized scientific journals by our experienced specialists in this field. , the introduction of modern historical methods used in world historiography into the historiography of Uzbekistan by summarizing the scientific literature published in the historiography of foreign countries on the history of our country using comparative analytical methods, further clarifying the topic of scientific research to determine a specific historical period, an actual historical thematic direction, the historical and geographical region of the chosen topical thematic direction., the result of the study is to determine the main direction of the historiography of the Silk Road to unify the historical thematic direction. In the history of Uzbekistan, there is every reason to study the Great Silk Road, as there are sources and literature on the positive impact of the Great Silk Road on the development of science and culture, the development of ancient cities, the development of diplomacy, the establishment of economic and cultural ties. Analyzing the development of the intercultural civilization of the peoples of Eurasia on the Great Silk Road, one can distinguish a separate direction "historiography of the civilization of the cities of the Great Silk Road".

Educational processes on the history of the Great Silk Road are being actively carried out in the universities of Uzbekistan. Education in this area is carried out at several universities in Uzbekistan. In particular, there are classes on the history of the Great Silk Road at the Faculty of International Education Programs of Samarkand State University, t "Silk Road" International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage and the University of Oriental Studies. Therefore, Uzbekistan has all the grounds to teach the history of the Great Silk Road. Consequently, it is important to organize the teaching process using new methodological technologies in teaching these lessons. Studying the history of the Great Silk Road and developing it as a special course in educational institutions is one of the urgent issues facing today's historians. When analyzed from the point of view of historiography, by analyzing foreign literature written about the Silk Road, it is important to introduce new information unknown to the field in the history of Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. Agnew Neville. (1997) Conservation of Ancient Sites on the Silk Road. Los Angeles, The Getty Conservation Institute. 112 p.
2. Ambolt, Nils. Caravan. Travels in Eastern Turkestan. London, Blackie&Son. 1939.24-84 p.
3. Abdukholik A. (1994) The Great Silk Road // Communication.Tashkent. 54-65-p.
4. Amarasinghe P. (2023) Revival of the Silk Road legacy. Examining how China uses history to legitimize its «Belt and Road Initiative» HISTORIA I ŚWIAT, nr 12. <https://doi.org/10.34739/his.2023.12.23>
5. Bagchi, Prabodh Chandra. (1955) India and Central Asia. Calcutta, National Council of Education. 5-17 p.
6. Beckwith Christopher. (2009) Empires of the Silk Road. A History of Central Eurasia from the Bronze Age to the Present. Princeton, Princeton University Press. 7-12 p.
7. Berdimurodov A. (2017) The Great Silk Road. Uzbekistan Publishing House. Tashkent press. 197 p.
8. Bernard Ollivier. (2020) Walking to Samarkand: The Great Silk Road from Persia to Central Asia. 312 p.
9. Bonavia Judy. (1992) The Silk Road. Xi'an to Kashgar. Hong Kong, Odyssey. 3-8 p.
10. E. Knobloch. (1962) The Heart of Asia (travel), in Czech, Prague, Bratislava.
11. E. Knobloch. (1965). The Death of Tamer Lane (a novel), in Czech, Prague. 114-118 p
12. E. Knobloch. (1965) The art of Central Asia. Paul Hamlyn, London.
13. E. Knobloch. (1972) Beyond the Oxus: Archaeology, art & architecture of Central Asia. Benn, London. ISBN 0-510-03351-2.
14. E. Knobloch. (2001) Monuments of Central Asia: A guide to Turkestan's archaeology, art and architecture. I. B. Tauris, London. ISBN 1-86064-590-9.
15. E. Knobloch. (2002) The archaeology and architecture of Afghanistan. The History Press, Stroud. ISBN 0-7524-2519-6. 54-65 p
16. E. Knobloch. (2013) Treasures of the Great Silk Road. The History Press. 354 p.
17. Frankopan. P. (2015) The Silk Roads (a new history of the world). – London. Bloomsbury Press. 656 p
18. Hansen. V. (2012) Silk Road a new history. -London. Oxford University Press. ISBN139780190218423. 320 p.
19. Hedin, Sven. (1938) The Silk Road. London, George Routledge & Sons Ltd. 5p.
20. Hopkirk, Peter. (1980) Foreign Devils on the Silk Road. The Search for the Lost Cities and Treasures of Chinese Central Asia. London, John Murray.
21. Jacqueline M. Moore, Rebecca Woodward Wendelken. (2010) Teaching the Silk Road: A Guide for College Teachers. SUNY Press.
22. Khojayev A. (2007) The Great Silk Road: relations and destinies. -Tashkent: UzME,280 p.
23. Kobzeva O.P., Djalilov O.Z. (2015) Uzbekistan and China on the Silk route (Monograph). – Tashkent.103 p.
24. Liu, Xinru. (2010) The Silk Road in World History. New York, Oxford University Press. 3-12 p.
25. Robin Brown. Marco Polo: the incredible journey. “The History” press. 2011. 184p.
26. Lourence Bergreen. Marco Polo: from Venice to Xanadu. Alfred A.Knoff press. New York. 2007. 510 p.

27. Jonathan Clements. "A history of the Silk Road. House publishing. London.2017. 220 p.
28. Mavlonov O. (2001) From the history of the formation and development of ancient roads in Central Asia. Collection of materials of the Republican conference. -Tashkent: Academy. 112 p.
29. Nebenzahl Kenneth. (2004) Mapping the Silk Road and Beyond. 2000 Years of Exploring the East. New York, Phaidon Press.
30. Nile Green. (2014) Writing Travel in Central Asian History. Indiana university press.
31. Tucker Jonathan. (2003) The Silk Road. Art and History. London, Philip Wilson. 24-27 p.
32. Whitfield Susan. (1999) Life Along the Silk Road. London, John Murray. 7-9 p
33. Whitlock Monica. (2002) Beyond the Oxus. The Central Asians. London, John Murray.
34. Wood Frances. (2003) The Silk Road. Two Thousand Years in the Heart of Asia. London, British Library.
35. Wilfrid B. (1973) The Golden Road to Samarkand. London, Hamish Hamilton. 17-23 p.